

Protocol: Efficient AI-supported quantification of network structures in SEM imaged human mucus

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Workflow Overview

All raw images to be analyzed must be contained in an input folder. The ImageJ Macro must be provided with the file path of the input folder, the model-file of the machine-learning classifier that should be applied, and the file path of an output folder that will contain the processed images and a data table with pore and filament data for each image. To avoid manual pooling of the data tables, a python script is provided, that can be used to pool all the single data tables into one file. All the single steps needed for a successful application are described below. Additionally, two short tutorial videos are provided along this protocol.

The python pooling script needs the following packages to work: *os*, *pandas*, *tkinter*, *numpy*, *matplotlib*, *seaborn*, and *scipy*. You can install them using pip in the command line with the following syntax: *pip install <package>* e.g., *pip install numpy*. We developed and tested the pooling script using Thonny (<https://thonny.org/>).

We also provide a python script for the automatic sorting of images for the input folder based on text recognition (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15148693>). We usually image regions of interest with different magnifications but found those images with a magnification of 50.000 X best for the automated analysis. To avoid manual sorting of hundreds of images we developed a python script that loads the individual images and checks the magnification by text recognition in the meta data field at the image bottom. The script then copies only images of the desired magnification in the input folder.

Training a new Machine-Learning Classifier (e.g. Multilayer Perceptron)

1. Preparing Training Data

To (re)train the machine learning classifier you first of all need to prepare a sample of training data. For this select a subset of the image set you want to analyze. This should be around 5 - 10% of the total number of images. So if you want to analyze 100 images, select 5 to 10 that show all morphological variety that occurs within the image set. Open all the images in Fiji as

separate files (1) and run the *Preprocessing_for_MLP_training.ijm* macro (2). The macro will apply the selected preprocessing steps like intensity equalization or background correction (3).

The processed images are then combined to an image stack and a central region is cropped. Then the trainable weka segmentation plugin is called (4). Load the *Default_MLP_Classifier.model* file with "Load classifier".

2. Redesign of the neural network (optional)

Under “settings” you can adjust the machine-learning classifier architecture before retraining. You can change the training features (1) and by clicking on “MultilayerPerceptrone” (2) you can change the number of hidden layers and neurons within the layers (3).

3. Labelling and refinement

To retrain the classifier, mark regions on the image and add them to the corresponding classes (2). Then press “Train classifier” to start the training process. First the training feature stack will be created.

Afterwards the graphical user interface with a visualization of the neural network will open. If it is not opened automatically just press “Train classifier” again. Under “Controls” press the *Start* button (1) to begin the training. The number of epochs will increase with each training step and the Validation error per Epoch (2) should decrease over time, showing that the model gets better in identifying the labeled structure. The training will terminate after 500 epochs but it can also be stopped manually by pressing the *Stop* button (1). Press the *Accept* button (3) to finish the training.

4. Save model and data

The retrained classifier will then automatically be applied to the images and show the classification of all pixels in the colors of the classes. With the *Toggle overlay* button (1) you can hide and show the classification colors. If the classification is insufficient, you can annotate new regions and add them to the classes and train the classifier again. Do this until you are satisfied with the results.

You can now save the classifier (2) and use it for your full image set. You should also save the training data (3). This allows you to later load the training images and the already annotated regions again and continue the refinement of the model.

Analysis step-by-step guide

1. Preparing input and output folders

We recommend preparing a project-specific folder for each batch analysis run. Within this project folder you should place the input and output folder, as well as the macro and classifier that was used. If you change analysis parameters, you should either directly change them in the macro code or document them, so that you can always reproduce the analysis. If you change or retrain the classifier, you should also document which classifier was applied.

2. Start the macro and select folders and MLP

Start ImageJ/Fiji (1) and open the Analysis Macro (2) by *File>Open* or *drag and drop*. Then press the *Run* button. You then need to select (3) the file paths for the input and output folder and the file format of the raw images (tif on default). Then press the *OK* button. Afterwards, select the machine learning classifier model you want to apply (4).

3. Select analysis parameters

Before the analysis starts, you need to select the analysis parameters. These are the pixel size and unit (we set the default to 2.233 nm which is the pixel size of our devices at 50.000 X magnification), the counting frame (default on 5 % but we found you can easily go up to 30 % to get more data from your images), and the checkbox for the intensity equalization which normalizes the contrast of the images, which we found useful for our setup.

4. Check output data

After the analysis is complete, the output folder should contain a data table, an overlay and a binary image for each analyzed raw image. The counting frame is shown in the overlay in cyan and the deep pores are outlined in red, and the shallow pores are outlined in green. The filaments between all pores (shallow and deep combined) are shown in blue and junctions in magenta. The data table contains the information of the area and minimum Feret diameter of the red and green outlined pores and the length and width of the blue filaments. Only structures within the counting frame or those touching the upper or right edge are analyzed. Structures outside of the counting frame or those touching the bottom or left edge are excluded from the analysis [1].

Output folder with processed images

Analysis Overlay

Binary classification

Pore area (deep)	Pore diameter (shallow)	Pore diameter (deep)	Length	Width
6178.012	54.563	29568.694		
423.835	20.097	8755.923	89.320	
5494.890	70.947	837.697	22.684	
418.848	17.331	418.848	20.527	94.739
8591.376	72.837	1480.928		
12969.338	85.758	2552.980		
1266.517	32.512	1401.147		
6113.190	69.117	628.272	19.824	
7643.981	79.569	1815.009		
1431.065	22.988	543.506	19.818	
259.287	15.790	812.765	19.199	239.342
708.053	18.955	1271.504		28.952
2762.404	44.660	1655.448		

Results data table

5. Pooling of the data sets (optional)

After you checked the output data and are pleased with the results based on the validation overlay, you can now pool the data from the image area-wise data tables, possibly after you deleted the data tables from insufficiently analyzed images. To do so, you have to execute the python

pooling script (1) provided along this protocol. The script will load all the txt files in the selected folder (2) and combine all the values of the columns. After successful data pooling a single Summary.txt (3) will be saved in the selected folder and an overview of the pooled data (3) will be given, in the form of several violin and box plots as well as one histogram with the filament width distribution.

1

```

1 import os
2 import pandas as pd
3 import tkinter as tk
4 from tkinter import filedialog
5 import numpy as np
6 import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
7 import seaborn as sns
8 from scipy import stats
9
10 # Define expected columns
11 COLUMNS = [
12     'Pore area (deep)', 'Pore diameter (deep)', 'Pore area (all)',
13     'Pore diameter (all)', 'Filament length', 'Filament min width',
14 ]
15
16 def set_axis_to_lower_95_percent(ax, data_list):
17     """
18     Set y-axis limits to start at 0 and show lower 95% of data
19     """
20     # Flatten the data if it's a list of arrays
21     all_data = np.concatenate([d for d in data_list if len(d) > 0])
22
23     # Calculate 95th percentile
24     p95 = np.percentile(all_data, 95)
25
26     # Add some padding (5% of p95)
    
```

2

Select folder containing .txt files

Organisieren Neuer Ordner

Name	Status	Änderungsdatum	Typ
input folder	✓	06.05.2025 10:48	Dateiordner
output folder	✓	06.05.2025 10:59	Dateiordner

Ordner: output folder

Ordner auswählen Abbrechen

3

Summary

Figure 1

Pore areas comparison

Category	Median	Mode	SD
Deep	1375.1	1857.1	6336.5
All	1396.2	1911.9	77541.1

Pore diameter comparison

Category	Median	Mode	SD
Deep	40.4	30.9	39.6
All	31.3	17.7	56.2

Deep Filament measurements

Category	Length	Median	Mode	SD
Deep	Length	154.6	95.4	137.4
All	Length	151.1	41.4	59.5

Deep Filament width vs count

Category	Length	Median	Mode	SD
Deep	Length	154.6	95.4	137.4
All	Length	151.1	41.4	59.5

References

1. Gundersen, H.J.G., *Notes on the estimation of the numerical density of arbitrary profiles: the edge effect*. Journal of Microscopy, 1977. **111**(2): p. 219-223.